

Minutes of the 51st Experimenters' Meeting
The Cosener's House, Abingdon, Thursday 27th June 2013
(This document was finalised on 2nd August 2013)

Present:

Dr Bogdan Antonescu⁶ (BA)
Mr Les Dean^{1,4} (LD)
Dr Jon Eastment^{4,5} (JDE)
Dr David Hooper^{4,5} (DAH) Secretary
Dr Chris Lee⁷ (CFL)
Dr Graham Parton^{2,5} (GAP)
Dr Jeremy Price³ (JP)
Prof Geraint Vaughan⁶ (GV) Chair

Apologies

Emily Norton (EGN), Hugo Ricketts (HMAR), Dirk Klugmann (DK), Jon Jones, Mariana Adam, and Mark Salkovskis, all had to cancel their attendance of this meeting at the last minute.

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Other abbreviations used in this document:

ARISE Atmospheric dynamics Research InfraStructure in Europe
BL(WP) Boundary-Layer (Wind-Profiler)
COPE CONvective Precipitation Experiment
DE David Edwards (Met Office)
DPW Dave Wareing (University of Manchester technician)
EUCOS EUMETNET Composite Observing System
FGAM Facility for Ground based Atmospheric Measurements
MSE Mesosphere Summer Echo
MST(R)(F) Mesosphere-Stratosphere-Troposphere (Radar) (Facility)
NERC Natural Environment Research Council
NLC Noctilucent Cloud
PC Personal Computer
PV Potential Vorticity
RMS Root Mean Square
UM Unified Model
UPS Uninterruptable Power Supply
UT Universal Time
VSWR Voltage Standing Wave Ratio

1. Minutes of the previous meeting

The minutes of the 50th meeting were accepted without correction.

2. Matters arising

ACTION ITEM 46.5.3 GAP and DK to investigate the possibility of storing data from all of the Met Office's new Jenoptik Laser Cloud Base Recorder (LCBR) on the BADC.

ONGOING

GAP reported that there were still a few small issues to sort out but that he hoped to make progress in the near future. GV emphasised the high importance of volcanic ash detection work. He added that there had been another incident in the last week, with ash from a volcano in the Alaskan Peninsula appearing over the British Isles. This is not expected to cause any flight disruptions. Dave Wareing (DPW) had recently managed to fix the Elight lidar, which subsequently detected the ash layer from the MST Radar site.

ACTION ITEM 49.4.1 DAH to investigate, prior to carrying out action item 47.2.2, the cause for clearly-erroneous data points in the Met Office wind-profile messages being flagged as reliable.

COMPLETED

ACTION ITEM 47.2.1 DAH to modify the MST radar signal processing software, as soon as possible, to allow it to make use of updated Python programming libraries.

ONGOING

ACTION ITEM 47.2.2 DAH to ensure, as soon as possible, that MST radar data products generated by the latest version of the signal processing software are available for the entire observation archive.

ONGOING

A report of 49.4.1 is given in Section 6a.

ACTION ITEM 47.3.2 DAH to recreate cloud base altitude files, starting from 2nd November 2010, with the time stamps corrected.

ONGOING

This remains a low priority task.

ACTION ITEM 48.4.2 DAH and JDE to investigate the opportunities for returning the spare MST radar transmitter to working order.

ONGOING

Although LD has recently gained a much better understanding of how the transmitters work, he is not yet sure whether the spare unit can be returned to working order. Many of its components were used to repair the other transmitters, following lightning strike damage in December 1999. GV suggested that DAH should consider buying a new transmitter. JDE cautioned that a new transmitter might not

integrate effectively with the existing ones.

In relation to action item 49.3.1 (which had been completed by the time of the 50th meeting), GV commented that the Met Office had done a good job of forecasting the prolonged rain event of 8th/9th June 2012. However, owing to their low confidence in the forecast, they did not issue a warning.

ACTION ITEM 49.5.1 GAP to create a link from the Cardington dataset webpage on the BADC to the FGAM wind-profiler page.

ONGOING

ACTION ITEM 50.5.1 EGN to liaise with GAP in order to sort out the archiving of BLWP data on the BADC.

ONGOING

GAP reported that he had been in contact with EGN regarding the boundary-layer wind-profiler (BLWP) data archive. He will create the link to the Cardington dataset when this is completed.

ACTION ITEM 50.3.1 DAH and LD to implement a method of restoring lost broadband connections without anyone having to be at the radar site.

COMPLETED

Details of this action are given in section 3b.

ACTION ITEM 50.4.1 DE to send DAH a list of the organisations that operationally assimilate the Aberystwyth MST Radar data.

COMPLETED

DAH reported that the data are currently being operationally assimilated by the (UK) Met Office, Météo France, (Swiss) Météo Suisse, (German) Deutscher Wetterdienst (DWD), and the European Centre for Medium-range Weather Forecast (ECMWF). The details, which are updated on a monthly basis, can be found at <http://www.metoffice.gov.uk/research/weather/ewinprof/profiler/data-assimilation>. Since the data are made available through the World Meteorological Organisation's (WMO's) Global Telecommunication System (GTS), it is possible that other organisations are making use of them also.

3. Facility Report - DAH

3a) Electricity

The Uninterruptable Power Supply (UPS) units have indicated brief (~ 1 s) electricity supply disruptions on 3 occasions during the past six months: on 31st January 2013, 1st June, and 16th June. There was a 13 s disruption on 26th January 2013. None of these had any impact on the equipment being powered by the UPS units.

3b) Telecommunications

The modem lost its broadband connection at around 06:20 UT on 27th January 2013 and at around 04:51 UT on 12th May. Despite the fact that both occasions were on a Sunday, LD visited the site later the same day (at around 15:00 UT) in order to power-cycle the modem, thus re-establishing the connection.

In relation to action item 50.3.1, DAH purchased a GSM-Auto remote control switch - <http://www.gsm-auto.com/> - in early February 2013. A mobile phone text message can be used to activate one of its relays for a predetermined length of time. LD wired the broadband modem's dc power supply through the relay so that the modem could be power-cycled remotely. However, poor mobile phone reception at the radar site initially proved to be a limiting factor. Consequently LD added an external antenna - a high-gain 868 MHz Yagi - to the system. The MST radar was stopped on the afternoon of 20th May 2013 so that LD could optimise the antenna's pointing direction. He thought that this would be easiest to do in a radio-quiet environment. Unexpectedly, he got the best signal strength when the antenna was pointing towards the side of the valley.

The modem lost its broadband connection just a few days later - at around 22:12 UT on 23rd May 2013. This gave DAH the chance to test the new device in earnest. He successfully power-cycled the modem as soon as he spotted the problem the following morning, i.e. at around 07:05 UT on 24th May. He was similarly successful in remotely restoring the connection at around 10:50 UT on (Saturday) 1st June 2013. It had been lost at around 22:50 UT the previous evening.

DAH opted to use the giffgaff mobile phone network. This piggy-backs on the O2 network, which is known to give better reception than most at the radar site. However, O2 does not appear to offer a simple pay-as-you-go tariff. The giffgaff tariff requires at least one chargeable call to be made every six months. This can be achieved by instructing the GSM-Auto unit to send its signal strength reading via a return text message. The GSM-Auto unit costs approximately £140 and the external antenna cost an extra £50.

3c) Miscellaneous site issues

DAH had mentioned at the time of the last meeting that the wooden shed next to the lidar container was being renovated. This principally consisted of the wood on its westward-facing side being replaced. Honey bees had temporarily set up hives on this side of the shed, in the gap between the inner and outer walls, during the summers of 2010 and 2011. Although some impressive-looking honey comb was recovered as a result of the renovation, there was no honey.

DAH had also mentioned been mentioned at the last meeting that willow tree saplings had become established within the south-west corner of the MST radar antenna array. There were so many of them that the only effective way to remove them was to scrape off the top soil. The radar was powered down for the whole day on 8th March 2013 to allow this to be undertaken.

Approximately 20 Environmental Science undergraduates from the University of Manchester visited the radar site on 13th April 2013. DAH talked to them about the MST radar whilst GV talked to them about the lidars.

The roof-felting on some of the primary power splitter huts, which are found within the MST radar antenna array, suffered from wind damage during the early part of 2013. LD had to carry out some repairs during late April and early May.

4. NERC Instrument Report - DAH

Full details of instrument performance issues can be found at http://mst.nerc.ac.uk/cgi-bin/mstlog_public/mst_event_search.py.

4a) Campbell Scientific surface met sensors

There have been no problems with these sensors during the past 6 months. LD explained that he had fitted a piece of nylon rope through the inlet of the tipping bucket raingauge. This allows the water to pass through freely, but filters out anything which is likely to lead to a blockage.

4b) Campbell Scientific surface wind sensors

It was not possible to establish a dial-up connection to the data logger at Frongoch between 26th and 29th January 2013. This appears to have been the result of a failed telephone/broadband filter, which, in turn, is attributed to thunderstorm activity on 26th January. Since the Frongoch data logger can only accumulate just over 2 days' worth of data before it starts to overwrite the oldest data, approximately 10 hours of data were lost. GV pointed out that the surface wind data are scientifically very useful. He asked DAH to increase the logger's storage capacity so that dial-up problems do not result in data losses.

ACTION ITEM 51.4.1 DAH to increase the storage capacity of the Frongoch data logger so that communications failures do not lead to data loss.

NEW

LD pointed out that Frongoch is now connected to Aberystwyth University via a fibre-optic cable. However, in order to take advantage of this, the data logger would need to be interfaced through a local computer. DAH wondered whether a Raspberry Pi could serve such a role. It would have the advantages, over a regular PC, of being much cheaper and of consuming considerably less power. JP pointed out that they use Moxa mini-computers for such tasks at Cardington. However, these cost several hundred pounds each.

DAH changed the time of the Frongoch data downloads from 10:00 UT to 02:30 UT on 13th April 2013. The 10:00 UT time had been introduced during the summer of 2001, when at least 3 modems (both at the radar site and at Frongoch) were destroyed as a result of nearby thunderstorms. Tony Olewicz subsequently disconnected the site modem overnight as a protective measure. This required the automatic download time to fall after his usual arrival on site. However, it also meant that the previous day's quick-look plot was not available to DAH first thing in the morning. The new arrangement allows him to see the previous day's data from all instruments at the same time.

4c) Vaisala WXT510 surface met and wind sensors

A short data gap in the raw data file for 26th May 2013 caused a problem for the netCDF file creation software. Consequently files for this date have not yet been released onto the BADC.

4d) Vaisala LD40 laser ceilometer

The instrument failed to collect any data for a few hours on the mornings of 3rd and 30th March 2013. In both cases the error message revealed: "*Test laser failure. No more measurements possible.*". Previous problems of this kind have been associated with very low air temperatures. In both of the above cases, the temperature was close to -5° C when the problem began and the instrument began to operate normally again once the temperature had risen to a few degrees above zero.

4e) Sky-camera

There have been no issues with this instrument over the past 6 months.

DAH reported that he would soon be supervising a work experience student, who will be required to identify interesting atmospheric phenomena in the sky-camera images. Five previous students have already contributed to this project, which has now covered the first year sky camera operations, i.e. April 2007 to April 2008 - http://mst.nerc.ac.uk/sky-camera_event-log.html.

4f) Noctilucent Cloud (NLC) Camera

DAH reported that the 2013 NLC season had started early (in late May) and that NLCs had been visible from the British Isles on many nights. The Chilbolton-based camera had so far seen NLCs on the mornings of 3rd and 10th June 2013. The MST radar had seen a brief Mesosphere Summer Echo (MSE) on 15th May. This is approximately a week earlier than MSEs seen in any other year. However, there was little subsequent activity until 27th May 2013, when an MSE persisted for over 5 hours.

DAH reported that he had recently given a popular science talk on the subject of NLCs and MSEs. He expects to have enough material for a research science seminar by the end of the summer. He aims to write up this work for a peer-reviewed journal. GV suggested that this would be a good topic for a regional Royal Meteorological Society meeting in Manchester. He also suggested that DAH should engage with the UK MIST (Magnetosphere, Ionosphere and Solar-Terrestrial) community in order to find the appropriate scientific audience.

CFL is developing an interest in the mesosphere from his work with the ARISE (Atmospheric dynamics Research InfraStructure in Europe) project. He suggested that DAH might be interested in airglow data, which give temperatures at around the mesopause level. He offered to put DAH in touch with the group that makes airglow observations from Maynooth in Ireland (53.2°N, 6.4°W).

4g) MST Radar

The radar has not suffered from any significant problems over the past 6 months. This is reflected by the fact that the EUCOS model-comparison statistics - for timeliness, availability and quality - were all comfortably within their target values. DAH has inferred that data are considered to be unavailable, rather than untimely, if they are delivered more than six hours late (they are targeted to arrive within 30 minutes of the end of the averaging period). This is based on the daily statistics for October 2012, which David Edwards (DE) from the Met Office provided for him (DAH only has access to monthly statistics). The modem lost its broadband connection for almost 48 hours, i.e. approximately 6% of a month, starting on Saturday 6th October. The backlog of data would have been delivered as soon as the internet connection was re-established. Nevertheless, the monthly timeliness value was 98% whereas the availability value was just 94%.

GV commented that he found the model-comparison statistics provided by the Met Office more-illuminating than those provided by EUCOS. Since they include comparisons of both radiosonde and radar data against the model, they can indicate where limitations of the model rather than of the observations are responsible for differences between the two. Moreover, they can give an indication of the magnitude of biases as well as of random errors and show how these vary as functions of altitude. GV requested that DAH therefore focus on the Met Office's statistics for future meetings. He further requested that, since these statistics constitute a unique component of metadata, DAH should make them permanently available if the Met Office will allow this.

ACTION ITEM 51.4.2 DAH to make the Met Office's model-comparison statistics for the MST radar permanently available to users if the Met Office will allow this.

NEW

The maximum useful altitude for wind-profiling purposes was noticeably below average during the first 10 days of June 2013. DE contacted DAH to find out if there was anything wrong with the radar. However, DAH thinks that high pressure conditions, which persisted throughout this period, typically lead to such reductions. The performance improved at the end of the period without any intervention having been taken.

The most-commonly-occurring problem suffered by the radar over the past 6 months has been interference: on 15th and 17th February 2013, 28th March, 13th and 16th April, 18th May, and 19th June. Most instances lasted for less than 15 minutes. The longest (on 13th April 2013) lasted for 2 hours. For the most part, the signal processing was effective at avoiding contamination, although the vertical velocities at around 12:15 UT on 18th May 2013 were affected. The short duration of these episodes and their low frequency of occurrence do not give DAH any cause for concern.

Another commonly-occurring problem was the transmitter for antenna sector B shutting down with an

analogue error: on 17th February 2013, 15th March, 5th and 7th May, and on 3rd, 4th, and 5th June. In most cases it was approximately 20 hours before LD was on site in order to restart the transmitter. However, since the noise floor was not raised, as happened when the transmitter for antenna sector A suffered from a similar problem, any reduction in useful altitude coverage was barely noticeable. LD adjusted the transmitter's measurement circuitry on 6th June 2013 in order to prevent this problem from recurring. DAH had mistakenly assumed, when updating the instrument performance log, that these problems were caused by the transmitter blowing its choke. However, LD pointed out that the choke issue had been infrequent over the past year.

There have been a few minor issues with the new beam steering hardware. Between Saturday 4th and Tuesday 7th May 2013 (a Bank Holiday weekend), the beam steering controller sent frequent messages about high Voltage Standing Wave Ratio (VSWR) values (> 2.5 ; typical values are < 1.5) for quad 16. The performance of the radar does not appear to have been affected by this. The radar was briefly powered down on the morning of the 7th to allow LD to swap beam steering unit for that quad.

The beam steering unit for quad 95 began reporting high (> 2.5) VSWR values on the morning of 22nd May 2013. LD visited the site later in the day in order to swap it for a spare unit. He found that water had accumulated inside. He assumed that the water had worked its way into the dipole assembly of one of the antennas and then seeped down the connecting cable into the beam steering unit. He disconnected the antenna and put a dummy load in its place.

On 25th and 26th May 2013, the supply voltage for the beam steering unit on quad 14 flipped repeatedly between a value of around 0.3 V and its expected value of around 24 V. LD visited the site on Sunday 26th in order to swap the affected unit at around 11:20 UT. However, he accidentally swapped the unit for quad 4 rather than 14. He quickly realised his mistake and swapped the unit for quad 14 at around 12:15 UT. In both cases, LD switched the transmitters into a non-transmitting state before swapping the beam steering units.

LD had reduced the output power levels on the transmitters for antenna sectors B and C when they had been giving frequent problems. However, now that they are more stable he has been increasing the power levels. The setting for sector B was changed from 2 (out of 5) to 3 at around 11:25 UT on 21st June 2013; that for sector C was increased from 1 to 2 at around 11:25 UT on 18th June and from 2 to 3 on 25th June.

5. Guest Instrument Report

5a) FGAM instruments - GV

It had been reported at the previous meeting that the BLWP was recently upgraded. However, a number of problems have been encountered over the past 6 months. These are thought to be the result of software changes. In particular, the data for the lowest few range gates are unreliable. The instrument is currently being installed in Cornwall for the COPE (CONvective Precipitation Experiment) field campaign. DAH asked whether the MST radar should make any special observations in support of the campaign. GV clarified that interest was so focused on the Cornish peninsula that MST radar observations are unlikely to be of direct use.

The Leosphere lidar is currently in a working condition. The Elight lidar had some laser problems, although DPW recently managed to fix it. This was timely as it subsequently detected volcanic ash from Alaska on the night of 25th/26th June 2013. The ozone system has been upgraded, which means that all of the Elight's functionality can now be controlled remotely from Manchester.

CFL reported that a proposal is being put together for a follow-on to the current ARISE project. If it is successful, it will aim to install new instruments and will be looking for new partners. MST radars and lidars will be useful for delivering information about gravity waves. GV suggested that it would be

useful to operate a cloud radar next to the MST radar. He is considering this as part of a future project.

5b) Other Guest Instruments - DAH

There was no report on the Met Office's GPS (Global Positioning System) Receiver, owing to the fact that Jon Jones had to cancel his attendance of the meeting at the last minute.

Two air-sampling instruments were installed at the radar site during March 2013: an ultraviolet laser induced fluorescence spectrometer from the University of Manchester and a trapping sampler from Aberystwyth University. The central aim of the project is to improve understanding of biogenic cloud condensation nuclei. Samples from the second instrument can be brought back to the lab for microscope and genetic analysis. This information will be used to test the spectrometer's ability to discriminate between different classes of biological particles. The Manchester instrument is currently supporting the COPE campaign but will return to the radar site at the end of the summer.

6. Science and technical presentations

6a) The cause of rogue MST Radar winds - DAH

This investigation relates to action item 49.4.1. The version-3 MST radar signal processing software - which is described in detail in the paper at <http://www.ann-geophys.net/26/3253/2008/angeo-26-3253-2008.html> - has been in operation since January 2006. It employs a variety of quality control steps, including tests for both radial and temporal continuity of wind components. This makes it particularly effective at rejecting outlying data points. Consequently, DAH was surprised to learn that on rare occasions it flags clearly-erroneous winds as being reliable. Such rogue winds are confined to just a few consecutive range gates and, as DAH has now established, to single cycle of observation. DE had discovered their existence from enhanced daily values of the EUCOS "quality" parameter (DAH only has access to the monthly values).

DAH has traced the source of the problem to the horizontal wind speed θ_s compensation factor. This is needed to correct for the fact that the radar return signal power typically decreases with increasing zenith angle (a phenomenon that is commonly referred to as aspect sensitivity). For an off-vertical radar beam, this leads to the side of the beam that is closest to the zenith being weighted more-strongly than the side that is furthest away. The effective beam pointing zenith angle is therefore slightly smaller than the nominal angle. The horizontal wind speed can be underestimated by up to 30% if this is not taken into account. The compensation factor is derived from the ratio of the radar return signal powers for observations made at 4.2° and 6.0° off-vertical.

DAH has discovered that all of the the rogue winds are associated with spikes in the signal powers for observations made at 4.2° off-vertical. These lead to overcompensation of the horizontal wind speeds. In one case, characterised by near-neighbour speeds of 20 m s⁻¹, rogue speeds of 159, 1106, and 268 m s⁻¹ were found at 3 consecutive range gates. The software is supposed to cap the compensation factor at 50% in order to avoid such problems. DAH has not yet determined the reason for this not happening. The cycles starting at the following datetimes are known to be affected: 2011/05/22 22:37:39, 2011/05/29 06:23:04, 2011/09/02 21:56:06, 2011/12/04 15:27:56, 2012/02/04 09:23:32, and 2012/06/01 18:13:44 UT.

CFL questioned whether the compensation factor should be applied at all. Although he recognised that it made sense theoretically, his own analysis of MST radar winds (see next section) had revealed that it increased the random measurement error. GV pointed out that its main role was in reducing systematic errors. He therefore wondered if climatological values might be more-appropriate than those calculated on a cycle by cycle basis. DAH was of the opinion that variations over time scales of half an hour or more reflected changes in the nature of the underlying scattering mechanism. Nevertheless, he conceded that low-pass-filtering the values in time might be the best way of minimising both systematic and random

errors. GV concluded that this issue should be investigated before DAH reprocessed the entire dataset.

ACTION ITEM 51.6.1 DAH to determine an improved method of applying the horizontal wind θ_s compensation factor so that its contribution to random errors is minimised.

NEW

6b) Uncertainty in MST radar horizontal winds - CFL

The aim of this work is to estimate the uncertainty in the horizontal winds derived from MST radar observations. The focus is on random rather than systematic errors. CFL has made use of data from campaign periods, during which radiosondes were launched from the radar site. He has exploited the fact that MST radar observations are made using complementary (off-vertical) beam pointing directions. The radial velocities can be combined to give estimates of the vertical velocity that are independent from those derived from vertical beam observations. The uncertainty in the horizontal wind is estimated from the root mean square (RMS) difference between the two vertical velocity estimates projected onto the horizontal.

The analysis shows that the uncertainty has local maxima at the lowest range gates and at around the jet/tropopause altitude. The values increase somewhat with increasing wind speed. The values (at all altitudes) are significantly smaller than the RMS differences between radar and radiosonde-derived winds. This suggests that although radar-radiosonde comparisons might reveal biases between the two, they will overestimate the random errors in the radar derived winds. CFL concluded that much of the variability between single cycle estimates of radar-derived winds represent actual variability rather than measurements errors. Consequently these single cycle estimates should be used when correcting observed spectral widths for the effects of beam broadening. However, owing to the difference between the radar and radiosonde measurement principles, time-averaged radar winds should be used when comparing against radiosonde winds. CFL thought that a 30 minute averaging period was about right.

6c) Climatology of convective storms and tropopause folds over Wales - BA

BA had intended to give a joint presentation with HMAR. However, since HMAR was in possession of the presentation material and had cancelled his attendance at the last minute, BA gave a short verbal update.

Tropopause folds appear as double layers in radiosonde data and so BA has been making use of ozonesonde data, which show up the folds more clearly. He has access to data from 407 ozonesondes that were launched during the 1990s. Folds were seen in 47 of these. Since the MST radar only began quasi-continuous operations in late 1997, simultaneous data are not available for all of the ozonesondes. BA commented that the radar data were typically the most useful for detecting folds.

GV added that that tropopause folds commonly give rise to multiple bands in radar return power (this has been revealed by John Lawson's work on frontal passages). The mechanism appears to be that the fold drags dry upper-tropospheric air down with it. The resulting sharp gradients in humidity give rise to enhancements in signal power. Consequently the signal power feature can have a deeper vertical extent than the fold. Although there can be multiple structures in the shear also, the most prominent one identifies the fold location.

6d) A case study of a cold frontal passage - GV

This relates to 29th November 2011, which fell during an Intensive Observation Period of the DIAMET (DIAbatic influences on Mesoscale structures in ExTropical storms) and TROSIAD (TROpopause folding, Stratospheric Intrusions And Deep convection) campaigns. BA had launched 7 radiosondes from the MST Radar site on this day. Two cold fronts - the first one an ana type and the second one a kata type - had approached the British Isles from the west before merging. The rainfall radar plots show rain bands to either side of the merged front. It is clear - from a sharp drop in temperature, from a

local minimum in pressure, and from a sharp rotation of the wind vector - that the surface front passed over the MST radar site at around 13:00 UT. The Chilbolton 3 GHz radar was also in operation and the FAAM (Facility for Airborne Atmospheric Measurements) aircraft was flying in radial directions relative to it, albeit over the southern Irish Sea.

Jeffrey Chagnon has run the Unified Model (UM) for this day. He has focused on the Potential Vorticity (PV) at the 500 mbar level. There is a band of enhanced values ahead of the front. According to the UM, this is the result of diabatic processes. Although GV is not convinced that this is the most appropriate way to think about the feature, he concedes that he would not have been aware of its existence if it had not been for the model results. He thinks that the enhanced PV values might arise from a change in vorticity, i.e. primarily from a horizontal shear in the wind. The pattern of winds generated by the WRF model is close to that observed by the MST radar, albeit at slightly later times. GV is not yet sure what the feature is (he thinks that it looks like a bore wave). Nevertheless, he is pleased that he has excellent observational data for allowing comparisons to be made against the models. Jeffrey Chagnon is keen to follow up on this case study.

7. Any Other Business

GV pointed out that he would be involved in an overseas campaign during January and February of 2014. He therefore requested that the next Experimenters' meeting be held during late November or early December of 2013.